

**HISTORICAL SUSTAINABILITY AND DYNAMISM OF CRIMINAL AND CUSTODIAL
PUNISHMENT POLICY. CRIME OR DISEASE?**

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Abstract

In this essay will be researched creative ideas about criminal and punishment policy of states and converting them to new innovations, also decriminalization and alternatives of penalty, contemporary challenges, rehabilitation and mediation, significant questions in this field and future perspectives. This particular topic has been chosen for research because, repeating sentencing has not provided fundamental “victory” on criminal environment and it is inadequate with new modern progress in each field of public management.

Objectives: This article is going to find reasons of this “non-improving” of policy and also discuss the principle of developed perspectives of sentencing. It is important for legal practitioners and students during their course of interaction with this field and cases and will contribute also psychological researching about illegal human behaviors.

Keywords: decriminalization, custodial punishment, rehabilitation, mediation, isolation.

Methods: Will be used overview from criminological, medical, psychological and philosophical position, will be analyzed details of criminal punishment policy. Through the study, will be clarifying problems by asking questions addressed to readers. The objective of this methodology is to stimulate critical thinking and encourage readers to develop their own answers.

Introduction:

Crime will be regarded as an illness, and this illness will have its doctors who will replace your judges, its hospitals that will replace your prisons. Liberty and health will be alike. Balm and oil will be poured where iron and fire were once applied. This evil, once treated with anger, will be treated with charity. It will be simple and sublime. The cross substituted for the gallows. That is all.

March 15, 1832

Victor Hugo

“The Last Day of a Person Sentenced to Death”(1)

This is 2026, after roughly two centuries, however nothing from above mentioned was happened, expect partly terminating of death penalty or disappearing of “glyodin”. Prisons still exist, and judges were not replaced with doctors. Visa versa there are some offences which sanctions are expanded and extended, myriad human behaviors were criminalized, as well as. Whereas, in this period science and information technology developed sharply, and international community have unified for eradicating organized criminality and its dangerous types. In international level were adopted several legal documents to combat against particular crimes, also in this purpose were created global platforms or organizations for collaboration states.

Why legal approaches were not transferred to medical or psychological? Crime or disease? Which theory will serve civilization? Why all these efforts did not cause for discovering biological roots of diseases in human body and healing them? What are the obstacles

in a way moving of such tendencies? Why recidivism is increasing from time to time instead of decreasing? How eradicate human illegal and amoral intentions even partly?

Viktor Hugo was not alone, for last two centuries we can face myriad of theories with suggestions of medical care of offenders instead of penalty, as well as accepting all illegal acts as an illness. There were numerous attempts for finding roots of crimes in human brain, blood, and other organs. Scholars thought that after diagnosing it would be possible to heal mental diseases and eventually eradicate it ultimately. Indeed, investigators achieved to discovery several types, such as drug dependency, affectional or sexual aggression and others, and also found effective healthcare procedures. However, achievements could not cover the most popular kinds of crimes – theft, fraud, robbery, assault, domestic violation, hooliganism, which are committed more than others. But what was the content of their work? And are there any positive consequences from these theories for the field of criminology? How and where determine traits of desire for gaining illegal material benefit? Which human organ indicates initiation to commit crime? Are these indicators inmate or we get them through our life? If based several scholars, some positive important human abilities, also talent, intellect or physical power are transferred through blood or genes from generation to generation. Is criminal initiation among them or we become criminals in result of environments affect or under social conditions? Unfortunately, despite of arguable positions, science could not answer these questions, fundamentally. Rather than, findings and inventions could not be utilized effectively.

To discuss these questions would be impossible beyond famous Italian scholar, “father of criminology” Cesare Lombroso (2). His theories are still very prominent, with the topic of brain pathology, the changes happening in the brain because of diseases and illnesses. He had founded of theory “born criminal”, “atavism”, positivistic school of criminology, and others. (3)

Lombroso's theory – “born criminal” that all children are born with these evil character traits and all criminals show some kind of degeneration mark. Normal people can also have some of these marks, but they appear less frequently. A mark can be a receding forehead and a certain size of the head in proportionality to the body, which is why Lombroso and his school measured the size of the head of inmates. His observations made him conclude that murderer had bigger heads and that bigger heads occurred less often in female criminals than male ones. Other atavistic marks according to Lombroso are varieties of the ear like handle ears, broad hips for men, different number of vertebrae, unusually long hands.(5) But having one or more these physical characteristics wouldn't cause a person to commit a crime, they are rather an outward sign which point to other anomalies, like malformations of the brain, which could lead to committing a crime. His general theory of criminality saw criminal behavior as caused by biological factors which are recognizable and predictable by physiognomic features. (3,4,5)

Despite of broad criticism, Lombroso and his school are investigated still today. They believe possibility of predicting first criminal intention or recidivism due medical, psychological or other scientific sources. Opposite group of scholars created separate approach with several differences.

History of punishment policy did not accept any of them, and states preferred to provide physical measures and incarceration to criminals. Each state's custodial punishment strategy and relevant international legal documents demonstrate that the goal of punishment is to rehabilitate offenders and to bring them to community.

Article 10, International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (6) constitutes, “The penitentiary system shall comprise treatment of prisoners the essential aim of which shall be their reformation and social rehabilitation.”

The most accepted theory about punishment is rehabilitation — the idea that the purpose of punishment is to apply treatment and training to the offender so that he is made capable of returning to society and functioning as a law-abiding member of the community. Rehabilitation has gone through periods of support and criticism throughout history as an objective of punishment but still remains one of the main purposes relied upon by the courts in sentencing offenders. Established in legal practice in the 19th century, rehabilitation was viewed as a humane alternative to retribution and deterrence, though it did not necessarily result in an offender receiving a more lenient penalty than he would have received under a retributive or deterrent philosophy. In many cases rehabilitation meant that an offender would be released on probation under some condition; in other cases, it meant that he would serve a relatively longer period in custody to undergo treatment or training.

However, statistical information (even from open sources) would demonstrate separate view. Because, above mentioned theory couldn't find its approval through years. According numerous accessible reports on Internet about international, regional or territorial

criminal situation, recidivism rates are generally high across most countries.

When something happens once, it might never happen again. But if it happens twice, it will surely happen a third time.

Paulo Coelho
“The Alchemist” (7)

Recidivists are estimated to be responsible for a considerable proportion of all offences committed in any given year. From open sources repeat offending contributed to 20% of all offences, approximately. On the other hand, this is just about open-crimes, which are solved annually. It should be considered that these figures don't encompass latent or non-solving crimes? Obviously, they are committed in high professional level, with professional practical skills and knowledge gained during “criminal experience”. In result of this, to solve or to discovery them requires hard and long-term efforts.

There is considerable controversy over the effectiveness of custodial punishment in reducing crime. For example, most researchers have failed to find any systematic relationship between crime rates and imprisonment rates: it is equally probable for regions with high imprisonment rates to have high or low crime rates, while increases or decreases in rates of imprisonment are equally likely to be followed by increases or decreases in crime, and so on. Thus, the “three strikes” legislation passed in USA in the 1990s, which imposed mandatory prison sentences after three convictions, was found to have no effect on crime rates. (8) Even the death penalty, as noted above, appears to do little to reduce murder rates, since most jurisdictions that use it (including several U.S. states and various other countries) have substantially higher murder rates than jurisdictions that do not.

For example, United States has the highest murder rate and is virtually alone in using the death penalty. The state of Texas accounts for a very high proportion of all executions within the country (roughly half in the early years of the 21st century), yet it has continued to experience relatively high rates of murder and violent crime. In general, criminologists believe that severe punishments are not particularly effective in reducing high crime rates. (9)

Overall, the problem is not only for USA or other developed countries, even poor communities could not get effective results in custodial punishment system. The effect consists simple isolation of offenders and therefore protecting people from dangerous threats.

United Nations Standard Minimum Rules for the Treatment of Prisoners (the Nelson Mandela Rules). The Rule 4 shows “The purposes of a sentence of imprisonment or similar measures deprived of a person's liberty are primarily to protect society against crime and to reduce recidivism”. (10) Thus, additional target of custodial punishment is social isolation or to protect society from offenders and this was a main goal of states through history.

Other problem of custodial punishment police is high material expenditure of states. Several governments tend to release prisoners early, to ease prison overcrowding.

For example, in UK the population is forecast to rise to at least 94,000 by 2028 at current estimates, but maximum safe capacity is only 89,000. The 20,000 additional places promised by the New Prisons Program, which is recommitted to, won't be available until the 2030s. (11) Planning permission challenges in local areas have delayed the building of new prisons, and caused costs to spiral. The capital cost of a new prison place is up to £600,000 – but in 2015 the government committed to build 10,000 more places at the cost of £130,000 per place. The Government needs to consider a step change in its attitude to building prisons and transport infrastructure. (12)

Considering all, it has created questions for economists. How to economize government budget? Some scholars suggest to humanize custodial punishment policy, or to provide decriminalization.

Decriminalization is the process through which the legislature removes criminal **sanctions** against an act, article, or behavior which is considered a crime. Decriminalization means it would remain illegal, but the legal system would not prosecute a person for the act. This can be contrasted with legalization which is the process of removing all legal prohibitions against the act. Decriminalization is a legal concept with applications in many areas of criminal law, ranging from assisted suicide to so-called **victimless crime**.

Overall, decriminalization is a successful progress (13) and it has resulted several evaluations.

Actually, countries have criminalized the acquisition and use of certain drugs for over a century, and this approach has not stopped people from using illegal substances, decreased rates of substance use disorder or reversed the current overdose epidemic. The nationwide overdose crisis and its impact is a public health threat that demands immediate legal approach to save lives. By removing criminal penalties for drug possession, thousands of people can get health services. Since its passage, drug arrests and incarcerations have dropped. Due to a delay in providing funding for services, there was initially a delay in people accessing recover supports. Now that millions of dollars are starting to flow to service providers, people are accessing services in greater numbers.

However, in local and international legislation decriminalization process has gone slowly and in contrast, new types of human behavior have criminalized.

Other additional modern innovation in criminal policy is mediation. Mediation is a voluntary and private dispute resolution process in which a neutral person, the mediator, helps the parties to reach their own negotiated settlement agreement. The mediator has no power to impose a settlement, their function is to overcome any impasse and encourage the parties to reach an amicable settlement. The mediator may act as a shuttle diplomat and a channel for communication, by filtering out the emotional elements and allowing the parties to focus on the underlying objectives. The mediator

will encourage the parties to reach an agreement themselves as opposed to having it imposed upon them. Mediation has proven an outstandingly successful management tool for resolving difficult disputes. It is a means by which the parties can re-learn the basis of communication with which they can then resolve future disputes. Advantages of mediation are broad, it creates a supportive and constructive environment, provide time efficient and cost-effective confidential process.(14) More than half of all criminal cases referred for mediation were violent crimes. A mediation process was launched for roughly half of all criminal offences referred for mediation, and in more than 70% of the criminal mediation processes ended in a settlement. The financial value of the settlements in mediation also was very high. (14,15)

Overall, numerous such effective innovations are increasing within both international and domestic legislation, and their application is becoming widespread, covering a large scale.

Conclusion.

1. **First**, it has been observed that criminal and custodial punishment policies have not fundamentally altered; their primary concentration remains the isolation of offenders from society.

2. **Second**, it can be predicted that the criminalization of human behavior will increase, much like the appearance of new types of illnesses.

3. **Finally**, the article ends on an optimistic note regarding the achievements of rapid technological innovation. These advancements will likely lead to the discovery of new mechanisms to replace traditional courts, law enforcement, and custodial punishment. Furthermore, artificial intelligence will be capable of creating "artificial environments" for isolation, which will ultimately conserve human energy, financial budgets, state power, and other vital resources.

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